

THE WORD MU'JAM AND ITS MEANINGS**Mukhamedbabaeva Shahnoza Askarovna****Master, Oriental University****Academic supervisor: Kasimova Sarvinoz**

Annotation: This article examines several meanings of the word "mojam", which is often used in the lexicon of the Arabic language. In the article , there will be discussion about this word, which means "dictionary" in Uzbek, how first appeared in Arabic linguistics, who used it, what are its original lexical and terminological meanings, and what types of it exist today and other lexicologies.

Key words: *vocabulary, dictionary, lexicology, Arabs, non Arabs*

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются несколько значений слова «моджам», которое часто используется в лексиконе арабского языка. В статье пойдет речь об этом слове, которое на узбекском языке означает «словарь», как впервые появилось в арабском языкознании, кто его использовал, каковы его исходные лексические и терминологические значения, какие его виды существуют сегодня и другие лексикологии. .

Ключевые слова: *лексика, словарь, лексикология, арабы, аджамы.*

Language acquisition is the most important aspect for every person. When we study the science of linguistics, all its departments, be it phonetics or phonology, lexicography - lexicology, are of great importance in learning the language. The first manifestation of the science of lexicography was the linguist Khalil ibn-Ahmad al-Farohidi (100-185 AH), about whom the Egyptian lexicographer Husain Nassar wrote in his "Emergence of Arabic (lexicology) and development" provided information in his doctoral thesis. According to him,

Arabic linguistics reached a high level in 175 AH with the idea of creating a comprehensive dictionary and its implementation by Halil ibn-Ahmad al-Farohidi. [1:194] The dictionary he compiled is in Arabic. It was one of the first dictionaries to spread and made a great contribution to the development of Arabic linguistics.

Lexicography played a major role in the lives of Arabic-speaking and Arabic-learning peoples in the Middle Ages, and one of the linguists ibn-Khaldun wrote about it: due to his speech, the vocabulary of the language has been damaged and most of the Arabic words are being misused, and as a result, to achieve the purity of the language, to prevent the forgetting of the Holy Qur'an and hadiths, to preserve the vocabulary of the language by writing and recording. It is clear from the above that the reason for the violation of the purity of the Arabic language was the people who were Arabized and did not know this language well there was a need to develop dictionaries [2:86].

In this article, the name of this science is "lugat" in Uzbek, which is called "mu'jam" in Arabic, and "jam" is its root.- عجم we learn the meanings of the words that were not known to us before. To do this, we first think about when this word entered Arabic linguistics, who used it for the first time, what are its original lexical and idiomatic meanings, and what types of it exist today.

Ibn Jinni says: "Know that in the speech of the Arabs (ا ج م) a j m letters described with "ajuma" The opposite of the word "clarity and clear statement" occurs in the meanings of "uncertainty and concealment", ujma العجمة and the word means that the language is arrested. Regarding the man who could not express himself clearly – اعجم ajam, and for woman used as عجماء ajma. Another different meaning of the word ajam means "dumbness". In fact, a person who cannot express his opinion clearly is considered to be "ajam and ajama" - someone who does not know Arabic.[1:8]

Another meaning of the word Ajma also refers to creatures who are

deprived of the opportunity to express their thoughts. In addition, another meaning of this word means keeping silent. For example, this one استعجم الرجل -اي sentence سكت

means that a person kept silent. One of the names of noon prayer is "ajmaa" because its recitation is recited without making a sound.[1:8]

Look at the seed of a date and any other fruit, which is called ajam or ujaam, a wave whose voices are not heard and whose waters do not spray الموج - babun mu'jam - باب معجم - mavjun with a'jam sentence as a closed door - الأعمج expressed by the sentence [1:8]

"Ajma-vadi" means a hard rock growing in the ravines, ajuma means a strong, strong female camel, strength, strength, test and endurance are also expressed by the word ajma, for example, عجم فلانا - ajama fulan - tried so somebody.

عجمت العود - ajamat al-uvdu - he bit into something to see if it was soft or hard, العواجم - avajim - means teeth, because they are biting tools, الة عجمة - ajama - something bitten [1:8].

If we look at the first content عجم - ajam the meaning of the stem implies ambiguity and seems to be the opposite of plain statement, but if أعجمت الكلام - a'jamtul kalam If it is said, the meaning "I have clearly explained the matter" comes out, which contradicts the above meaning. That's why (عجم) are morphological changes in the root of the word ajam, that is, the appearance of the verb ajm - ajuma

الة ك تاب اجمت - ajama weight indicates a positive content, - with its transition to ajama weight indicates a positive content, - in the sentence ajamtul kitaba - I opened the book (that is, to remove uncertainty from it) [1:9] comes in the meaning. Based on this idea, the word "comprehensive" in the dictionary also means "clearly stated, explained". In istilah, mujam means a book containing a large number of language words arranged in one order, combined with methods of pronunciation, explanation and

interpretation of their meanings. Meaningful to him قاموس “qomus” word is widely used now and in the past and now.

However, Husayn Nassar said in the above-mentioned book that there is no information about when the word "mu'jam" was used for the first time in this form and meaning "mu'jam". When studying the existing works, it became clear that the first word was written by Abu al-Qasim Abdullah bin Muhammad al-Baghavi, known as Ibn Bint Mani', who was born in 214 AH, the author of large and small dictionaries. found in his works. [1:10]

Later, in the 4th century, this word was mentioned in many books. The most famous of them are Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn al-Hasan al-Naqqash al-Mawsili (d. 351 Hijri) "Great, small and medium dictionaries" compiled from the recitation of the Qur'an and the names in it, Abu al-Husayn "Dictionary of Sheikhs" by Abdul Baqi ibn Qani ibn Marzuq al-Baghdadi (351 AH) and "Great, Medium and Small Dictionary" by Abu al-Qsim Sulaiman, bin Ahmad al-Tabarani (360 AH) and Dictionary of Shaykhs by Abu Bakr Ahmad bin Ibrahim al-Ismaili (371 AH), "Dictionary of Shaykhs" by Umar bin Usman al-Baghdadi (385 AH), known as Ibn Shahin, Ahmad bin Ali known as Ibn Lal Al-Hamdani's Dictionary of Companions (398 Hijri).

But there is no information about when the above description was applied to linguistic dictionaries. Later, dictionaries began to be called with a less meaningful, specific name, i.e. qamws - "Qumus". lib means surrounding sea, boundless, extensive. This work of his was widely distributed in the hands of later scientists, a lot of scientific research was conducted on it, and it was called a dictionary. Later, this term became so popular in modern and advanced dictionaries that it even became a synonym of the word "linguistic complex".[1:11}

Nowadays, these two terms are the main names in the scientific research of lexicologists and in the naming of dictionary books. Dictionaries are one of the

main tools in learning general languages, but in Arabic they are more attached to the learning process than in other languages. Because the Arabic language is distinguished by its derivative and root system (stem) and morphological weights. It is no coincidence that in the history of Arabic linguistics there have been four schools of classification and arrangement of dictionaries. Therefore, students should be encouraged to work with a dictionary, be it electronic or book dictionaries, as their role and importance in acquiring language skills is great.

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